

A Study of Transportation Problem in Operations Research

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Abstract:

The transportation problem is an important topic in operations research that deals with the optimal distribution of goods from multiple sources to multiple destinations at minimum cost. This project focuses on understanding the basic concept of the transportation problem and its practical applications in real-life situations such as supply chain management, logistics, and product distribution. The main objective of the transportation problem is to minimize the total transportation cost while satisfying supply and demand constraints.

In this project, a simple numerical example is considered to explain the transportation problem. Methods such as the North-West Corner Method and Least Cost Method are used to obtain an initial feasible solution. The optimal solution is then discussed to show how transportation cost can be reduced efficiently. This study helps undergraduate students understand how mathematical models can be applied to solve real-world distribution problems effectively.

Keywords: Transportation Problem, Operations Research, Optimization, Supply and Demand, Cost Minimization

Introduction:

Operations Research is a scientific approach to decision-making that deals with the optimization of complex systems. It uses mathematical models, statistical techniques, and logical reasoning to help organizations use their resources efficiently. One of the important models in Operations Research is the Transportation Problem. The transportation problem is concerned with finding the most economical way of transporting goods from a number of sources to a number of destinations while satisfying supply and demand constraints. The main objective of this problem is to minimize the total transportation cost or time involved in the distribution process. It plays a vital role in logistics, supply chain management, production planning, and distribution systems. In today's competitive environment, efficient transportation is essential for reducing operational costs and improving customer satisfaction. The transportation problem provides a structured

method for allocating shipments in such a way that available supplies are fully utilized and customer demands are met. Various methods such as the North-West Corner Method, Least Cost Method, and optimality tests are used to obtain the best possible solution.

This study aims to understand the concept, formulation, and solution techniques of the transportation problem in operations research through simple examples. The project helps in developing analytical skills and demonstrates how mathematical models can be effectively applied to real-world transportation and distribution problems.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the basic concept of the transportation problem.
- To study the importance of the transportation problem in operations research.
- To learn how to minimize transportation

cost while satisfying supply and demand.

- To understand balanced transportation problems.
- To study different methods for solving transportation problems.
- To solve a simple numerical example using standard methods.
- To understand the practical applications of the transportation problem in real-life situations such as logistics and supply chain management.
- To show how mathematical models help in effective decision-making.

Study of Transportation Problem in Operations Research Description:

The transportation problem is a special type of linear programming problem in operations research. It deals with the optimal distribution of goods from several sources to several destinations at the minimum possible transportation cost. Each source has a fixed supply, and each destination has a fixed demand. The objective of the transportation problem is to determine how much quantity should be transported from each source to each destination so that the total transportation cost is minimized while meeting all supply and demand constraints.

The transportation problem assumes that the cost of transporting one unit of product from a particular source to a particular destination is known and constant. It also assumes that the total supply is equal to the total demand, which is known as a balanced transportation problem. If total supply and demand are not equal, the problem can be converted

into a balanced one by adding a dummy source or destination.

Transportation problems are widely used in real-life situations such as distribution of raw materials from suppliers to factories, delivery of finished goods from factories to warehouses or markets, and logistics planning. By using appropriate solution methods, organizations can reduce transportation costs, improve efficiency, and make better managerial decision.

Statistical Tools and Analytical Method:

Linear Programming Technique: The transportation problem is a special case of linear programming where the objective is cost minimization under supply and demand constraints.

North-West Corner Method: This method is used to obtain an initial feasible solution by starting allocation from the top-left corner of the transportation table.

Least Cost Method: In this method, allocations are made to the cells with the lowest transportation cost to reduce the total cost.

Vogel's Approximation Method (VAM): This method provides a better initial solution by considering penalty costs for each row and column.

Optimality Test (MODI / Stepping Stone Method): These methods are used to check whether the initial solution is optimal and to further minimize the transportation cost if required. Solved Numerical Example.

Example 1:

Example: Transportation from Factories to Warehouses A company has 2 factories and 2 warehouses.

Transportation Cost Table

Factory/Warehouse	W1	W2	Supply
F1	5	4	30
F2	6	3	20
Demand	25	25	50

Step 1: Check Balance Total Supply = $30 + 20 = 50$
 Total Demand = $25 + 25 = 50$ (Balanced) Step 2:
 Allocation (Simple Allocation)
 $F1 \rightarrow W1 = 25$ $F1 \rightarrow W2 = 5$
 Step 3: Total Transportation Cost
 $= (25*5) + (5*4) + (20*3) = 125+20+60=205$

Conclusion:

This example shows how goods can be transported from factories to warehouses at minimum cost by proper allocation. Transportation problem techniques help in reducing total transportation expenses.

Example 2:

Source	Supply	City A	City B	City C
S1	20	8	6	10
S2	15	9	12	13
S3	25	14	9	16
	Demand	30	20	10

Solution using Least Cost Method:

1) Lowest cost = 6 (S1→B)
 Supply S1: 20, Demand B: 20 → allocate 20 units
 New: S1 supply left = 0, B demand left = 0
 2) Next lowest cost = 8 (S1→A) but S1 is empty → skip
 3) Next = 9 (S2→A) & (S3→B) both cost 9 Choose
 S2→A: $\min(15,30) = 15$ S2 supply left = 0, A demand left = 15
 4) Next = 9 (S3→B) but B demand is 0 → skip
 5) Next = 10 (S1→C) but S1 empty → skip Next = 12 (S2→B) S2 empty → skip Next = 13 (S2→C) S2 empty → skip
 6) Next = 14 (S3→A): $\min(25,15) = 15$
 S3 supply left = 10, A demand left = 0 7) Finally, 16 (S3→C): $\min(10,10) = 10$ Final Allocation:
 S1→B: 20 units S2→A: 15 units S3→A: 15 units
 S3→C: 10 units Total Cost:
 $= 20 \times 6 + 15 \times 9 + 15 \times 14 + 10 \times 16 = 120 + 135 + 210 + 160 = ₹625$

Conclusion:

From the given city-wise transportation problem, the goods were successfully allocated

from all supply cities to demand cities by using the Least Cost Method. The total supply was equal to the total demand; hence the problem was balanced. After proper allocation, the minimum total transportation cost obtained was ₹625. This result proves that the transportation problem helps in finding a cost-effective distribution plan between cities. From the given city-wise transportation problem, the goods were successfully allocated from all supply cities to demand cities by using the Least Cost Method. The total supply was equal to the total demand; hence the problem was balanced. After proper allocation, the minimum total transportation cost obtained was ₹625. This result proves that the transportation problem helps in finding a cost-effective distribution plan between cities.

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